

Extraction-spectrophotometric Determination of Lead in Environmental Samples[†]

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Many spectrophotometric methods for determination of trace amounts of lead in complex materials have been reported¹. Most of these methods are tedious, time-taking and non-selective as many of the common ions generally associated with lead interfere. Hence in the present investigation an effort has been made to develop a highly selective, reproducible and sensitive method for the spectrophotometric determination of lead at trace levels in environmental samples. It is based on prior selective extraction of lead with *N*¹-hydroxy-*N*¹, *N*²-diphenylbenzamidine² in chloroform at pH 10.0±0.2. The chloroform extract is subsequently reacted with 4-(2-pyridylazo)resorcinol in order to enhance the sensitivity of the method. Most of the common ions associated with lead in real samples do not interfere.

Results and Discussion

The absorption spectra of the Pb^{II}-PAR complex obtained after extraction of Pb^{II} with HDPBA in chloroform exhibit λ_{\max} around 525 nm. The pH range for the complete extraction was observed at pH 7.2–11.5. Maximum and constant absorbance of the red Pb^{II}-PAR complex was found at pH

8–11. Hence for all extractions and development of colour, an optimum pH of 10.0 was maintained throughout. The complete extraction of Pb^{II} was observed when 250–2000 fold molar excess of HDPBA was used. For maximum colour development an excess of 4–7 fold molar PAR was required. Addition of more reagent increases the absorbance of the reagent blank. The compositions of the Pb^{II}-HDPBA and Pb^{II}-PAR complexes, determined by curve-fitting method, indicate the involvement of 2 HDPBA and 2 PAR for each Pb^{II}, respectively. Out of the various solvents tried, chloroform was chosen because of the higher colour intensity and selective extraction of the complex. For all extraction work an equivolume of each phase was kept and a shaking time of 2 min was sufficient for complete extraction of the metal. The red coloured Pb^{II}-PAR complex is stable for at least 12 h at room temperature (27°).

The Pb^{II}-PAR complex obeys Beer's law up to 7.5 $\mu\text{g Pb}^{\text{II}} \text{ ml}^{-1}$. The molar absorptivity of the complex calculated in terms of Pb^{II} is $5.18 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at λ_{\max} 525 nm. The Sandell's sensitivity of the method is 0.004 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$. Precision of the method was checked by taking 10 repli-

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cate samples each containing 25 $\mu\text{g Pb}^{\text{II}}$ per 25 ml of organic phase. The relative standard deviation of the method was found to be $\pm 1.2\%$. The detection limit of the method is $0.01 \mu\text{g Pb}^{\text{II}} \text{ ml}^{-1}$. The effect of diverse ions on the determination of $25 \mu\text{g Pb}$ was studied. 2 ml of 2% thiourea was also added prior to the extraction of Pb^{II} with HDPBA at pH 10.0 for masking Cu^{II} . The tolerance limit of the various diverse ions causing error less than $\pm 2\%$ are (mg in parenthesis): Cd^{II} , Zn^{II} , Ni^{II} (1.0); Cu^{II} , Fe^{III} , Hg^{II} , Bi^{III} (2.0); La^{III} , Al^{III} (2.5); As^{V} , V^{V} , Cr^{VI} (3.0); Co^{II} (3.5); W^{VI} , Mo^{VI} (4.0); Sb^{III} , Se^{IV} , Mn^{II} (5.0); Mg^{II} , Ba^{III} (7.0); tartrate (6.5), citrate (10), cyanide (5) and thiourea (12).

Application: The method has been successfully studied for determination of Pb^{II} in standard samples³, industrial waste water, coal and fly ash. The data obtained were compared by AAS and the results were found to be in good agreement with the present method.

Experimental

A Carl-Zeiss Jena 'SPEKOL' spectrophotometer and a Systronic 335 pH-meter were used.

The standard solution of lead(II) was prepared by dissolving lead nitrate (0.1598 g) in glass-distilled water (100 ml). The working standard solutions were prepared by appropriate dilutions and then standardised by dithizone method⁴. A 1.0 M KCN in ammonia was used. $6.9 \times 10^{-3} M$ or 0.2% w/v HDPBA in chloroform and $3.4 \times 10^{-3} M$ or 0.1% w/v PAR solution in methanol was prepared.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF LEAD IN ENVIRONMENTAL SAMPLES

Sample*	Lead found (ppm) by		Relative standard deviation of present method $\pm \%$
	Present method	AAS	
A	32.5	31.2	1.1
B	6.7	6.23	1.2
C	118	116	1.2
D	96	93	1.1
E	13.8	13.2	1.3

*A=U.S.G.S. Standard 1 (BHVO-1), Pb = 31.2 ppm; B=U.S.G.S. Standard 2 (G-2), Pb = 6.23 ppm; C=fly ash, NTPC, Korba, India; D=coal ash, Baikunth Cement Plant, Indta; E=total waste water, Bhilai Steel Plant, India.

Ammonia-ammonium chloride buffer⁵ was used for all pH adjustment.

All chemicals were of A. R. (B.D.H. and E. Merck).

Procedure: To an aliquot of the solution containing upto 75 μg lead was added KCN solution (2 ml). pH of the solution was adjusted to 10.0 by adding ammonium chloride-ammonia buffer solution in a total volume of 10 ml aqueous phase. A 0.2% HDPBA solution (10 ml) in chloroform was added and the mixture shaken vigorously for 5–7 min. The phases were allowed to separate. The aqueous phase was discarded. The PAR solution (0.5 ml) was added to the organic phase and the made upto 25 ml. The absorbance of the reddish coloured complex obtained was measured at λ_{max} 525 nm against reagent blank.

In case of water sample, its volume was reduced to 10 ml and Pb^{II} was determined as above. For solid sample, it was digested with aqua regia and the excess HNO_3 was removed by heating with concentrated HCl. The dried residue was dissolved in 0.5 M HCl, diluted to 100 ml with 0.5 M HCl and amount of Pb^{II} determined as above.

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